

Deliverable D10.1

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Deliverable title:	Mapping between data elements	
WP No.	10	
Lead Beneficiary:	1: EMBL	
WP Title	Integrating disease related data and terminology from samples of different types	
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WP leader:	Alvis Brazma	1: EMBL
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1 Executive summary

Translational bioinformatics is an emerging field that studies how to use biomolecular data and knowledge for advancing medical care. This necessitates closer collaboration of specialists in bioinformatics and clinical informatics. One important aspect here is to make the information about existing biomaterials, which are stored in different biobanks, widely accessible for researchers.

The BioSamples database at EBI aims to serve as a definitive resource for managing biological sample information from a wide variety of data sources. In WP10 we are working towards integration of the BioSamples database with biobanks and biobank federations.

BBMRI has developed a set of recommended attributes that describe biobanks and sample collections within biobanks, expressed in the MIABIS standard. We have mapped MIABIS into SampleTab, a standard format for uploading and representing data in the BioSamples database.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Linking disease-related data to molecular information: terminology		V
2	Linking disease-related data to molecular information: data	V	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Translational bioinformatics is an emerging field that studies how to use biomolecular data and knowledge for advancing medical care. This necessitates closer collaboration of specialists in bioinformatics and clinical informatics. One important aspect here is to make the information about existing biomaterials, which are stored in different European biobanks, widely accessible for researchers.

BioSamples database at EBI aims to serve as a definitive resource for managing biological sample information from a wide variety of data sources, enabling users to easily explore this space. In BBMRI there are efforts to aggregate information about the contents of individual biobanks into sample availability catalogues (BBMRI portal, also other initiatives like French BIOBANQUES infrastructure). One step towards enabling more efficient research is linking the BioSamples database to the biobank information, and with this deliverable we report on our progress in this direction so far.

3.1.1 Motivation for a BBMRI/ELIXIR data bridge

The motivation for biobanks (or biobank consortia) to make their sample data available through the BioSamples database is the wish to advertise their collections with a view to set up clinical/translational research collaborations, to locate assays performed on specific biobank samples and to have a stable accessioning system supporting multiomics studies. Users would prefer to access a single database (BioSamples) instead of tens or hundreds of databases to establish where potentially interesting samples are located. They may then request access rights to the selected biobank, and in future will be able to easily navigate from the BioSamples database to biobank databases.

3.1.2 BioSamples database

The BioSamples database [1] aggregates sample information for reference samples frequently used in biomolecular research, e.g., Coriell Cell lines, and samples for which data exist in one of the EBI's assay databases such as ArrayExpress, the European Nucleotide archive, or PRIDE. Examples from ArrayExpress include biological sample information on HCT116 human colon cancer cells from the ATCC resource (experiment E-MTAB-651), mouse brain cancer samples with or without gene knock-outs (experiment E-MTAB-1303), or genetically modified Arabidopsis buds (experiment E-MEXP-3770). It provides links to assays for specific samples, and accepts direct submissions of samples. BioSamples uses various ontologies and controlled vocabularies including EFO and NCBI Taxonomy to perform queries, and supports ontological annotation of the data. The aim of BMB WP10 is to add another data source to this resource – biobank sample availability data.

Submissions to the BioSamples database should be in SampleTab file format, a tab-separated spreadsheet-like text format compatible with popular office tools. The two main information categories in the BioSamples database are BioSamples and Sample Groups. The definition of a BioSample is flexible in order to accommodate a wide range of uses. Typically each BioSample corresponds to a discrete physical object that is composed of live biological material, for example, a tissue sample or a cell line. The basic structure for describing BioSamples is an attribute which is composed of a key and a value (a key/value pair), as well as optional modifiers. A BioSample is described by a set of attributes.

BioSamples are collected together into one or more Sample Groups, which may also have attributes. A SampleTab file contains one or more Sample Groups, any BioSamples contained in those groups, and the attributes describing those BioSamples and Groups. A SampleTab file also contains general information, such as contact information, any publications related to the BioSamples, and URIs of the submitting resource e.g. a specific biobank. This is provided in the Submission block of SampleTab.

3.1.3 Biobanks and BBMRI

A Biobank is a collection, management and distribution centre of human biological samples, such as blood, tissues, cells or DNA; and/or related data such as associated clinical and research data.

Pan-European Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure (BBMRI) aims at building a coordinated, large scale European infrastructure of biomedically relevant, quality-assessed biobank samples. Some of the concrete goals of this effort include facilitation of transnational combination and exchange of biological materials and data, and reducing the fragmentation of the scientific community. The MIABIS effort (“Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing”) aims at facilitating biobank data discovery through harmonization of data elements describing a biobank at the aggregate level [2]. It consists of 52 attributes describing biobank’s content. Two main concepts are described via MIABIS attributes: biobanks and sample collections. This separation exists because:

- one study can be conducted with samples from multiple biobanks and, additionally, one biobank can host biological samples collected within multiple (unrelated) studies;
- since a sample collection can exist without requiring a particular study, the term “sample collection” is preferred over “study”.

3.1.4 BBMRI – ELIXIR data bridge in action

Stage 1. Biobanks submit data about their samples to BioSamples, using the SampleTab file format. It is important that biobanks follow their local rules and regulations with respect to data privacy so that only information that can be publicly accessed is exported to the BioSamples database. Data provider form, a component of the Ethical Governance Framework of BMB, will have to be completed by all biobanks providing data. The access to BioSamples is open, no sensitive information on human subjects is stored (though an access control mechanism is provided to allow submission of pre-publication confidential information). As BioSamples database does not impose local minimal requirements, it is up to individual data submitters, or groups such as BBMRI, to consider how much information can be provided, and to offer

standards which BioSamples can use to validate data. In some cases it might be only summary information about groups of samples, while it could also be anonymised information on individual samples.

Stage 2. Researchers interested in finding samples relevant for their research query BioSamples. They can access more information on interesting samples if they have the necessary access rights. There are two options how this could work:

- Users log into the corresponding biobank system when accessing a sample/group of samples belonging to that biobank. As this option relies entirely on the already working data-safety measures of the biobanks, no further contribution of the BMB security framework (WP5) is needed.
- If there is a common federated authentication/authorization system for BioSamples and the participating biobanks, users could log into BioSamples and be able to access biobank data more transparently.

Stage 3. If researchers are not authorized to access the information they need, they can apply to the relevant Data Access Committee (DAC) of the corresponding biobank. After access is granted and the DAC decision implemented by the biobank, users can return to stage 2. If the DAC application process is supported by an online workflow, as is currently being explored in a pilot project between the EGA database at EBI and the NordiCDB¹, then there is a scope for federated authentication also in this stage.

3.2 Work plan

The plan of working towards this Deliverable was as follows:

- maintain contacts between ELIXIR and BBMRI;
- select specific BBMRI resources for BioSamples population - either BBMRI federated infrastructure, or individual biobanks;

¹ Nordic Control Allele Frequency and Genotype Database:
<http://www.nordicdb.org>

- map BBMRI information into SampleTab;
- populate BioSamples database from the collaborating resource(s).

Population of BioSamples database from biobanks can be considered at several levels of granularity, supporting increasingly complex use cases. In order to have flexible and progressive data integration and to ensure interoperability with BMB workpackages we have addressed these levels in stages [3].

- Level 1: List of biobank cohorts and sample collections.
- Level 2: Additionally, data item dictionaries, protocols and templates.
- Level 3: Additionally, group level information.
- Level 4: Additionally, individual level data per item.
- Level 5: Additionally, identifiable data per individual.

Level 1 information is imported into BioSample database from the BBMRI.eu catalogue. Current EU privacy regulations, lack of individual level data exchange within BBMRI and lack of online data resources for individual biobanks make it impossible to go to Levels 4 and 5 for BioSamples population at this stage. Given this, we concentrate on mapping MIABIS information into BioSamples and SampleTab, in this way reaching data sharing on Level 2 and preparing groundwork for automated data exchange in future when biobanks will export data in a common format such as OMX [4].

3.3 MIABIS to SampleTab mapping

Table 1 lists all MIABIS concepts describing biobanks, alongside with corresponding fields in SampleTab describing the Submission. Since the submission section (“Meta-submission information” or “MSI” in the SampleTab specification) is not as easily extendable as the sample description section (see below), “Biobank ID”, “Biobank type” and “Contact phone” fields in MIABIS cannot be mapped to SampleTab. This will be considered for future versions of the format.

Table 1 Biobank level concept mapping

Attribute in MIABIS	Attribute in SampleTab
Biobank ID	--
Name of biobank	Submission Title
Juristic person	Person Last Name, Person First Name, Person Initials, Person Role, Organization Name, Organization Role
URL	Organization URI
Country code	Organization Address
Biobank type	--
Contact person	Person Name
Contact phone	--
Contact email	Person Email
Contact department	Person/Organization Address
Contact address	Person/Organization Address
Contact ZIP	Person/Organization Address
Contact city	Person/Organization Address
Contact country	Person/Organization Address
Hosted studies	groups in submission
Date of entry	Submission Release Date
Last Updated	Submission Update Date

Table 2 lists all MIABIS concepts describing sample collections, alongside with corresponding fields in SampleTab describing Sample Groups. The following named attributes are used: Group Name, Group Description, Sex, Age, Material, Count. For the remaining MIABIS sample collection attributes free-form SampleTab attributes are used. There are two types of these - Characteristic[] and Comment[]. Both allow free-form text in both the attribute key and value. Characteristics are used for attributes that encode biologically significant information. In our case these are used for encoding average age and disease state. The remaining attributes are mapped to the Comment field and will be considered for future extensions to the SampleTab format.

Although in SampleTab free-form text is allowed for most attributes, in the MIABIS template a few of the fields will be filled in by values from pre-defined lists. These attributes are “Type of Collection”, “Sex”, “Categories of data collected”, “Material type”, “Survey data”, and “Sample handling”; the corresponding lists of values can be found in the MIABIS definition paper. For the “Main diagnosis” attribute values will be ICD-10 codes. This constraint of the SampleTab attributes forms the first step in attribute formalisation and mapping needed for data integration and will be followed up in future work. The subsequent step is validation procedures marking a data set compliant e.g. to MIABIS and will be explored within WP3.

Some of the attributes (“Age interval”, “Average age” and “Storage temperature”) need to be qualified by the “Unit” SampleTab modifier used to specify units for numeric values.

Table 2 Sample collection level concept mapping

Attribute in MIABIS	Attribute in SampleTab
Collection ID	Comment[collection id]
Study name	Group Name
Description	Group Description
Sample Collection Responsible / Principal	Comment[responsible investigator] /

Investigator	Comment[principal investigator]
Contact person	Comment[contact person]
Contact phone	Comment[contact phone]
Contact email	Comment[contact email]
Contact department	Comment[contact address]
Contact address	Comment[contact address]
Contact ZIP	Comment[contact address]
Contact city	Comment[contact address]
Contact country	Comment[contact address]
Type of Collection	Comment[collection type]
Collection start	Comment[collection start date]
Collection end	Comment[collection end date]
Planned sampled individuals	Comment[planned sampled individuals count]
Planned total individuals	Comment[planned total individuals count]
Sex	Sex
Age interval	Age
Average age	Characteristic[average age]
Main diagnosis	Characteristic[disease state]
Comorbidity	Comment[co-morbidity available]
Categories of data collected	Comment[data type collected]
Material type	Material

Storage temperature	Comment[storage temperature]
Survey data	Comment[survey collected]
Medical records	Comment[medical records available]
Registers	Comment[register available]
Omics experiments	Database Name, Database ID
Sample handling	Comment[sample handling]
Current sampled individuals	Count
Current total individuals	Comment[current total individuals count]
Hosting biobank	Implicit relation to the submission that contains the current group
Date of entry	Comment[release date]
Last updated	Comment[update date]

3.4 Further work

We have described mapping to version 1.0 of MIABIS. A new version of the standard is expected, with a few of the new features being:

- Modular nature: the standard will contain core components (Biobanks and Samples Collections), as well as additional components that will be optional depending on the area in which data is exchanged, such as GWAS, rare diseases etc.
- More flexible means of describing diseases via structured links to disease ontologies, their versions and specific ontology terms.

As the MIABIS definition stabilizes, it is expected that biobanks will publish the biobank and sample collection descriptions in a format that complies with these guidelines. At that point automated conversion and import into

BioSamples database will be possible, the standard will be retrofitted to the data already submitted, and validation of attributes will be possible.

4 References

- [1] Gostev, M., Faulconbridge, A., Brandizi, M., Fernandez-Banet, J., Sarkans, U., Brazma, A., Parkinson, H. The BioSample Database (BioSD) at the European Bioinformatics Institute (2012) *Nucleic Acids Research*, 40 (D1), pp. D64-D70.
- [2] Norlin, L., Fransson, M.N., Eriksson, M., Merino-Martinez, R., Anderberg, M., Kurtovic, S., Litton, J.-E. A minimum data set for sharing biobank samples, information, and data: MIABIS (2012) *Biopreservation and Biobanking*, 10 (4), pp. 343-348.
- [3] Morris Swertz et al. Towards an intelligent framework to catalogue and search biobank (meta)data. (2012) HandsOn Biobanks conference, 20–21 September, Upsala.
- [4] <http://www.molgenis.org/wiki/omxManual>

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5 Adjustments made

As described in section 3.2 above, instead of mapping individual biobanks into BioSamples database we produced a mapping between MIABIS (a template defining how biobanks should describe their holdings) and BioSamples database. This result is applicable to a wider range of BBMRI data sources.

6 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 10; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 10 Title: Integrating disease related data and terminology from samples of different types

Lead: Alvis Brazma (EMBL)

Participants: EMBL, KI, UCPH

This work package will demonstrate the feasibility and provide a prototype for linking disease to molecular information on two levels – terminology and data. It has two tasks respectively – first to link ICD10 terms to gens and protein complexes, and second to link data in selected BBMRI biobanks to samples at the EBI BioSample Database supported by ELIXIR.

Both tasks are related, as to link biobanks to ELIXIR databases, the respective terminologies have to be mapped. For completing the first task we will create a prototype for an interoperable scheme linking IICD10 to genes and protein complexes. This will enable linking biobank and other phenotypic healthcare sector data on individuals to individual genotypes. Interoperability schemes of this kind will be essential for linking BBMRI and ECRIN data to the molecular level and for linking biobank and other phenotypic healthcare sector data on individuals to individual genotypes.

To accomplish the second task, we will select a small number of biobanks participating in the BBMRI infrastructure, with best advanced sample representation in databases. We will develop a model for linking sample objects to the respective objects at the BioSample database developed at EBI. The final deliverable in this work-package will be implementation of these links, allowing user to navigate from the selected biobanks to the EBI BioSample database and vice versa.

The work package will build upon standards developed in WP3, will utilize infrastructure build in WP4 and will benefit from data security framework developed in WP5.

Work package number	WP10	Start date or starting event:	month 13
Work package title	Integrating disease related data and terminology from samples of different		

	types		
Activity Type	RTD		
Participant number	1:EMBL	3:KI	15:UCPH
Person-months per participant	26	20	31
<p>Objectives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Linking disease-related data to molecular information: terminology 2. Linking disease-related data to molecular information: data. 			
<p>Description of work and role of participants</p> <p>Task 1. Mapping between sample information representation in a selected subset of resources. We will map data elements describing sample information in selected biobank databases that participate in the BBMRI federated infrastructure and the BioSample Database at EMBL-EBI. We will work jointly with WP3 to generalize the defined mappings and to develop the minimum standard that would enable to exchange this information.</p> <p>Task 2. The aim is to create a prototype which maps existing healthcare sector terminologies and their phenotypic descriptions to existing repositories linking diseases, symptoms and genes. More generally the aim is to embed the prototype efficiently into exiting computational linguistics, bioinformatics and clinical environments alike. In particular we will link phenotypic terminology in healthcare sector data to genes we will create a prototype for an interoperable scheme linking ICD9 an ICD10 to gene identifiers in ELIXR database concentrating on genes that have been associated with specific diseases, symptoms and tissues. The prototype will focus specifically on the generic ICD concepts and their mapping to relevant genetic information, and will not include efforts which aim for assigning codes and terminology to free text in healthcare sector data as it usually is done by text mining. The work on the prototype will also include language interoperability aspects on the terminology side, while considering only gene names as they are used in English.</p> <p>Task 3. The objective of this task is to demonstrate the interoperability of the sample representation at the EMBL-EBI's BioSample database, with the biobank databases participating in the federated biobank information</p>			

infrastructure created under BBMRI. This will also build upon the work done on terminology and identifier mapping. Working together with WP4 and WP5, we will implement a pilot for federated queries and secure links between a limited number of selected resources in BBMRI and the BioSample Database at EMBL-EBI (ELIXIR). A query system will be developed that will allow sample property based queries across these resources.